

Supplementary Text 1: Search Strategy

Supplementary Figure 1. Bivariate boxplot of the sensitivity and specificity in the included studies

Supplementary Figure 2. Funnel plot for publication bias.

Supplementary Text 1: Search Strategy

PubMed:

S.NO	SEARCH TERMS	RESULTS
#1	<p>"carcinoma, non small cell lung"[MeSH Terms] OR ("carcinoma"[All Fields] AND "non small cell"[All Fields] AND "lung"[All Fields]) OR "non-small-cell lung carcinoma"[All Fields] OR ("non"[All Fields] AND "small"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields] AND "lung"[All Fields] AND "cancer"[All Fields]) OR "non small cell lung cancer"[All Fields]</p> <p>Translations</p> <p>non small cell lung cancer: "carcinoma, non-small-cell lung"[MeSH Terms] OR ("carcinoma"[All Fields] AND "non-small-cell"[All Fields] AND "lung"[All Fields]) OR "non-small-cell lung carcinoma"[All Fields] OR ("non"[All Fields] AND "small"[All Fields] AND "cell"[All Fields] AND "lung"[All Fields] AND "cancer"[All Fields]) OR "non small cell lung cancer"[All Fields]</p>	98,902
#2	<p>"positron emission tomography computed tomography"[MeSH Terms] OR ("positron"[All Fields] AND "emission"[All Fields] AND "tomography"[All Fields] AND "computed"[All Fields] AND "tomography"[All Fields]) OR "positron emission tomography computed tomography"[All Fields] OR ("pet"[All Fields] AND "ct"[All Fields]) OR "pet ct"[All Fields]</p> <p>Translations</p> <p>PET/CT: "positron emission tomography computed tomography"[MeSH Terms] OR ("positron"[All Fields] AND "emission"[All Fields] AND "tomography"[All Fields] AND "computed"[All Fields] AND "tomography"[All Fields]) OR "positron emission tomography computed tomography"[All Fields] OR ("pet"[All Fields] AND "ct"[All Fields]) OR "pet ct"[All Fields]</p>	62,424
#3	<p>("diagnosis"[MeSH Terms] OR "diagnosis"[All Fields] OR "diagnostic"[All Fields] OR "diagnostical"[All Fields] OR "diagnostically"[All Fields] OR "diagnostics"[All Fields]) AND</p>	216,462

	("accuracies"[All Fields] OR "accuracy"[All Fields]) AND ("studies"[All Fields] OR "study"[All Fields] OR "study s"[All Fields] OR "studying"[All Fields] OR "studys"[All Fields]) Translations diagnostic: "diagnosis"[MeSH Terms] OR "diagnosis"[All Fields] OR "diagnostic"[All Fields] OR "diagnostical"[All Fields] OR "diagnostically"[All Fields] OR "diagnostics"[All Fields] accuracy: "accuracies"[All Fields] OR "accuracy"[All Fields] studies: "studies"[All Fields] OR "study"[All Fields] OR "study's"[All Fields] OR "studying"[All Fields] OR "studys"[All Fields]	
#4	#1 AND #2 AND #3	415

The following terms in various combinations were used during the search in EMBASE, ScienceDirect and Google Scholar:

('non small cell lung cancer'/exp OR 'bronchial non small cell cancer' OR 'bronchial non small cell carcinoma' OR 'carcinoma, non-small-cell lung' OR 'lung cancer, non small cell' OR 'lung non small cell cancer' OR 'lung non small cell carcinoma' OR 'non small cell bronchial cancer' OR 'non small cell cancer, lung' OR 'non small cell lung cancer' OR 'non small cell lung carcinoma' OR 'non small cell pulmonary cancer' OR 'non small cell pulmonary carcinoma' OR 'non-small-cell lung carcinoma' OR 'pulmonary non small cell cancer' OR 'pulmonary non small cell carcinoma') AND ('positron emission tomography'/exp OR 'pet scan' OR 'pet scanning' OR 'p.e.t.' OR 'positron emission tomographic scan' OR 'positron emission tomographic scanning' OR 'positron emission tomography' OR 'positron tomography' OR 'positron-emission tomography' OR 'tomography, positron') AND ('computer assisted tomography'/exp OR 'cat scan' OR 'cat scanning' OR 'computed tomographic scan' OR 'computed tomography' OR 'computed tomography scan' OR 'computer assisted tomography' OR 'computer tomography' OR 'computerised axial

tomography' OR 'computerised tomography' OR 'computerized axial tomography' OR
'computerized tomography' OR 'computerized tomography scan') AND ('sensitivity and
specificity'/exp OR 'sensitivity and specificity' OR 'specificity and sensitivity') – **1062 results**

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Supplementary Figure 2. Funnel plot for publication bias.

